

LESSON PLANNING AND CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT FOR LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS. DIFFERENTIATION PLAN

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Annotation. *This article discusses the importance of scaffolding and differentiation in teaching English language learners. Baecher (2011) explains that teachers need to adapt instruction to meet the diverse language abilities of students in the classroom. The article highlights practical strategies such as using visuals, modelling, sentence frames, and guided practice to support learners’ understanding. It also emphasizes that differentiation can be achieved through changes in content, process, and product. This source is useful for ESL teachers because it provides practical ways to support learners at different proficiency levels and helps create more inclusive and effective language lessons.*

Key words: *description of learners, objectives, Preliminary Lesson Plan Outline, Scaffolding, Differentiation, Justification,*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o‘rganayotgan o‘quvchilarni o‘qitishda scaffolding (bosqichma-bosqich yordam) va differensial ta’limning ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi. Baecher (2011) o‘qituvchilar sinfdagi o‘quvchilarning turli til darajalarini hisobga olib, ta’lim jarayonini moslashtirishi kerakligini ta’kidlaydi. Maqolada o‘quvchilarga tushunishga yordam beradigan amaliy strategiyalar, masalan, vizual materiallardan foydalanish, namuna ko‘rsatish (modelling), gap qoliplari (sentence frames) va yo‘naltirilgan mashqlar keltirilgan. Shuningdek, differensial ta’lim mazmun (content), jarayon (process) va natija (product) orqali amalga oshirilishi mumkinligi ko‘rsatiladi. Ushbu manba ESL o‘qituvchilari uchun foydali bo‘lib, turli darajadagi o‘quvchilarni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va samarali til darslarini tashkil etishga yordam beradi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *o‘quvchilar tavsifi, maqsadlar, dastlabki dars rejasi, scaffolding (bosqichmabosqich qo‘llab-quvvatlash), differensial ta’lim, asoslash*

Description of Learners

At the present time, I am working at the school of Internal Affairs, and I decided to choose the 6th-grade pupils. This class consists of 15 male pupils, aged 14-15, at a lower secondary school in Uzbekistan. Their first language is Uzbek, and they have two years of prior English learning. The English proficiency of my pupils is pre-intermediate, B1 according to the CEFR scale. They have a grammar-based curriculum with limited opportunities for communicative practice.

The learners attend English classes five times a week for 45 minutes. Their linguistic background is the same. I teach them General English for specific purposes (ESP) according to the curriculum. The classrooms are equipped with a whiteboard, projector, and basic visual materials. When my learners are motivated and energetic, they want a clear structure, routine, and active changes of activity to keep their attention. Their receptive skills, listening and reading, are stronger than their productive skills, speaking and writing. Learners’ listening skills are relatively stronger than their productive skills. They often listen to the teacher’s instructions and

textbook audio materials. They are motivated to listen when the topic is related to sports and physical activities, especially when visuals or videos are used. They do well with structured listening tasks such as matching, true/false, and short-answer questions. They have difficulties understanding natural speech, different accents, and fast conversation. They should be provided with more authentic listening input, such as short videos, dialogues, and interviews.

The weakest point of student is *speaking*. Some students are shy when they are asked to speak English in front of the class. They are motivated and energetic, especially when topics relate to sports and physical activity, and they prefer structured lessons with interactive tasks. They can not express their ideas in English confidently. Students often make pronunciation mistakes and have challenges in memorizing sentences. They need to do structured speaking activities such as

role plays, dialogues, surveys, and functional language. Eg: I like....., I play, My favourite sport is, Moreover, pair and group work can decrease their anxiety and build confidence.

The learners' *reading* skills are developed enough because they are taught grammar and textbook readings. They can understand short and simple texts with the necessary vocabulary. They have difficulty using reading strategies such as skimming and scanning. They are lack of identifying the main idea or specific information. The learners should be provided with short articles, posters, and dialogues.

Writing can be second weak skill for these learners. They can write short sentences and simple paragraphs using familiar structures. They like to write about interesting or personal topics, such as writing about their favourite sport or daily exercises. The learners have a limited vocabulary and grammar accuracy in writing. Their writing is usually guided by a teacher. They need to be provided with sentence models and word banks related to sports and fitness. They need to follow short paragraphs such as “My favourite sport”, “My Hobby”, and so on.

Objectives

- **Warm-up:(remember)**
SWBAT identify and describe different sports and fitness activities individually.
SWBAT draw their attention to the video recording, speak about the importance of sport and fitness individually [L], [S]
- **Pre-stage:**
SWBAT match the vocabulary list of words that are necessary for the lesson duration in individually. [R], [S]
SWBAT describe the photos of sportsmen and sports events individually. [S]
- **While-stage:**
SWBAT construct a list of the topic related sentences using the modal " should " in groups. [W]
SWBAT analyze the questionnaire according to the text in groups. [R], [W],
SWBAT justify the group discussion according to the role play in pairs. [S]
- **Post-stage:**
SWBAT design their group report by debating about Sport and Fitness in groups. [S]
SWBAT compose a sample set of rules for the citizens by using modal Should and the vocabulary given in the lesson in groups. [W]

Preliminary Lesson Plan Outline

- **Language Level:** B1
- **Age:** 14-15
- **Topic:** “Talking about Sports and Fitness.”
- **Time:** 45 minutes
- **Class Type:** General English
- **Warm up:** (5-min) Brainstorming [S]
- What should we do to be Healthy? (create mind map-based vocabulary)
- **Pre-stage:**(10 min.)
- Vocabulary Matching activity with key words (vitamins, minerals, lose weight, overweight, get fit, go/be on a diet) [W]
- Picture Description: students describe photos of sportsmen and Fitness and discuss the importance of sports with their partners. [S]
- **While-Stage:** (15 min)
- introducing the new theme: (Modal Should) [L]
- Reading for Gist and Detail: [R]
students read a short text and answer the comprehension questions
- Role play: Students are divided into pairs and create a problem-solving situation between a Doctor and a patient or a coach and an athlete. Students give advice using *Should*. [S]
- **Post-Stage:** (10 min)
- Debate: Should everybody do Sports to be Healthy? [S]
- Making up sentences using *Should*:
students in pairs try to create a presentation of a Healthy Lifestyle with the help of the vocabulary they learned.[W]

Scaffolding

All the activities are organized from simple to complex and from teacher-supported to independent learning.

At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher asks students some brainstorming questions and does mind mapping about a healthy lifestyle and sports. Visual prompts and guiding questions such as “*What should we do to be healthy?*”, “*What sports do you do?*” or “*How often do you go in for sports?*” The teacher models answers and writes key words on the board. This activity helps students prepare for the new theme. Tomlinson (2001) researches that “these variations were important in order both to move students along in their particular understanding and skills as well as to build a sense of community in the group”. (p. 2)

In the next step, students are introduced to new vocabulary such as vitamins, overweight, lose weight, get fit, and so on. The teacher provides pictures, definitions, and examples. Learners complete a matching activity with visuals. This activity is helpful to understand the new theme independently. In the further step, Students describe pictures of sports and fitness activities. The teacher gives students sentence starters such as “*He is ...*”, “*They are ...*” to guide speaking. Learners work in pairs to reduce anxiety and increase interaction. The teacher monitors and corrects errors gently. In the fourth step, the teacher introduces the modal verb *should* with examples and explanations. Students practice constructing sentences using guided prompts and

structured tasks. The teacher provides models and checks understanding through examples and short exercises. In step 5, students read a short text about sports and health. Then, students complete a questionnaire based on the text. Weaker students receive guiding questions, while stronger students answer open questions. In step 6, students perform role plays to give advice using *should*. Weaker students are given role cards. This stage encourages communicative use of language with less teacher support.

During the last step, students participate in a debate about sports and create a group report and written rules for a healthy lifestyle. The teacher’s support is minimal. Students use previously learned vocabulary and grammar independently. Peer feedback and self-correction are encouraged. As Tomlinson (2001) emphasizes, “the idea with product design for advanced learners is to ensure that learners actually have to stretch their information base, understanding, thought processes, planning and production skills and self-awareness”. (p.27)

In summary, I can say that all activities are applied from teacher-led activities to independent learner production. All materials as visual aids, modelling, sentence frames, guided practice, peer collaboration, and gradual task complexity, help learners move from understanding to confident communication. This lesson's progress provides all students, regardless of language level can successfully achieve the lesson objectives.

Differentiation

Level: B1

Students: 15

Age: 14-15

Types of learners: Low level -7, High level-8

Interests: Sport, Technology, and Art

Topic: Talking about Sports and Fitness

• **Warm up: Brainstorming. Healthy lifestyle mind map**

Types of Differentiation	Low-level Learners	High -Level Lerner
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lower-level students receive keywords and pictures. (sport, vitamins, exercise) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher level students add extra ideas(balanced diet , mental health)
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • teacher models ideas. weaker students work with partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger students brainstorm independently.
Product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students create a simple or extended mind map students depending on their level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students create a simple or extended mind map students depending on their level.

• **Pre-stage: Vocabulary matching:**

Types of Differentiation	Low-level Learners	High -Level Lerner
Content	learners are given the necessary vocabulary: for obesity, physical activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> learners are given the necessary vocabulary for physical activity and wellness
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> matching words with pictures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> matching words with definitions
Product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> completed matching worksheet or oral explanation of words. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> completed matching worksheet or oral explanation of words.

• **Post-stage: Writing Rules for a Healthy Lifestyle**

Types of Differentiation	Low-level Learners	High -Level Lerner
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> learners are given a word bank and sentence frames. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> learners are given Independent writing
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> guided writing with the teacher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> peer review
Product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> short list of rules: 5 sentences or extended written report: 8-12 sentences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> short list of rules: 5 sentences or extended written report: 8-12 sentences.

Justification

Scaffolding is essential for young EFL learners because it supports learners in moving from assisted to independent language use. According to Baecher, “A teacher might begin by thinking about the *base* activity they would design for their native speaking students who require little scaffolding.” (p 5).

In this lesson, scaffolding strategies such as modelling, visuals, sentence frames, and guided practice were used to support B1 learners in understanding sports and fitness content and using the model verb *should*.

Differentiation is necessary because learners have varying proficiency levels. And also, Baecher claims that “differentiated tasks should be manageable and achieved through small adaptation or they will become too daunting and time consuming for teachers”

(p. 6). Assessment data showed that some students are at CEFR A1 while others are at B1. Therefore, differentiation by content, process, and product was implemented. For example, weaker learners received sentence frames, while stronger learners produced independent sentences. Using assessment information allows teachers to provide with appropriate instructions and improve language outcomes.

REFERENCES

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